

A Method of Analyzing the Influence of Content on Collective Sensemaking in Social Media

Rita de Cássia Castro de Mendonça Negreiros ¹[0009-0008-5292-4236], José Orlando Gomes ¹[0000-0001-6838-714X], Tiago Cruz de França ²[0000-0002-1682-4587]

¹ Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, PPGI, Rio de Janeiro, RJ, Brazil
ritanegreiros@uferj.br, joseorlando@nce.ufrj.br

² Federal Rural University of Rio de Janeiro, Seropédica, Brazil
tcruzfranca@ufrrj.br

Abstract. The formation of meaning on social media is determined by how users interact with messages such as sharing, reacting, or commenting. In this study, the dissemination of information on social media was investigated using epidemiological modeling, specifically the Susceptible-Infectious-Recovered (SIR) model. The proposed method was applied to assess message on health surveillance issues and could help understand how users behave in contact with messages. The preliminaries results have shown the potential of the proposal to quantify the influence of messages on collective (users) sensemaking on social media.

Keywords: Social Media, Sensemaking, Epidemiological SIR model.

1 Introduction

Social media platforms play a pivotal role in facilitating dialogue, sharing opinions, and serving as valuable sources for collecting, extracting, and analyzing public opinion data [1]. This kind of content, which generates reactions, is then used to inform, and shape users' understanding of a subject. The process of how people assign meaning to a subject is referred to as sensemaking [14].

On one hand, social media have provided a voice to everyone; but on the other hand, there are no guarantees regarding the quality of information published on such platforms. Users can encounter both valuable information and misinformation or disinformation. While the influence of such information is known, there is a lack of methods to assess or measure the impact of content on social media users. Measuring the influence exerted by a message on social media users' sensemaking is a challenging task. Moreover, comparing whether a message (whether it contains accurate information or disinformation) has a greater or lesser impact than another is often determined subjectively based on human perception.

The research question presented in this paper is: "In the context of social media users, how can we measure the impact of the information they consume on their understanding (sensemaking) of a specific subject?"

The aim of this research is to quantify the influence of messages on social media's users sensemaking. Therefore, this paper presents the proposal to measure the influence of information shared on social media in shaping users' understanding using an SIR epidemiological model, which aims to identify and classify the sentiment expressed in text data, such as posts, to gain insights into the opinions, attitudes, and emotions of individuals or groups.

SIR (Susceptible-Infectious-Recovered) epidemiological models are used to model the spread of infectious diseases in a population. These models are a way to classify people based on their condition. This model was first used in 1927 by Kermack and McKendrick and was subsequently applied to a variety of diseases, especially airborne childhood illnesses with lifelong immunity after recovery, such as measles, mumps, rubella, and whooping cough and presents the three different statuses that the population could be in terms of a disease. [3]

Despite differences in sensemaking and SIR models domains, both share some parallels. In sensemaking, one can identify sentiment in posts over time and predict changes in public opinion, or trends in consumer preferences, natural disasters, or political crises. In SIR models, one can use changes in infection rates or number of cases over time to predict an epidemic or assess the effectiveness of different interventions. Quantifying the influence of a publication is the first step towards having a better understanding of the potential of that medium in a population and assessing the influence of the message on people. Prominent messages can provide insightful information about attention dynamics by showing what information a crowd finds particularly valuable during crisis events [4].

In this context, the objective of this work is to collaborate with the field of sensemaking analysis and the influence of information provided by social media users, analyzing different reactions to social media messages, proposing a model based on epidemiological models that highlights the relationship between user reactions on social media and certain types of epidemiological contamination. The results of this experiment intend to show the potential for understanding the impact collective sensemaking on social media.

The rest of this work is organized as follows: Section 2 contains the works found in the literature review. Section 3 describes the applied methodology. Section 4 details the analysis of the collected data and its results. And finally, Section 5 presents the final considerations.

2 Related Works

There is different research in the area of sensemaking and social media, focusing on Twitter, for example, identifying a set of tweets highlighted during the 2018 Hawaii False Missile Alert and analyzing the intersection of social media attention dynamics with meaning-making collective during crisis events [4]. Message analysis work also extracted from Twitter related to the protests that began in Brazil in June 2013, where it was analyzed, through polarity, information such as sentiment and public opinion, quantifying the messages of support and rejection of the protests [5]. Also capturing

public messages on Twitter about COVID-19 carried out by government authorities, classifying them as messages of guidance or disinformation [6].

Surveys capturing messages and their analysis, as well as the proposal in this work, help to understand and measure sensemaking in the population exposed to the messages created in the MS. As a unique aspect of this study, the aim is to analyze how a message can influence a certain population as a type of epidemic, through epidemiological models. This type of study creates opportunities for understanding the dimension of the influence of social media.

In the analysis of social media compared with the SIR model, we can see in the literature, that some users susceptible to certain messages will be able to write a related topic or leave comments, these belong to the infectious class and are called current authors in the context of the web forum. Some comments and readers will post to other threads, infecting others with their posts. This interactive process leads to the flow of discussion about a topic from one author to another. After a certain period of time, some authors stop participating in discussions and lose their power to influence others, so they say they are recovered. This dynamic can be compared to epidemiological models such as the SIR model [7].

2.1 Sensemaking

In addition to being an individual cognitive process, sensemaking is also a collective one in which social connections and shared meanings are important components [2]. The usage of social media is vital for organizations for many leaders and managers, as decisions and interpretations have the potential to affect the general understanding. Harmonizing social media behaviors has been found to need collective sense-making based on common values and beliefs [13].

2.2 The SIR Model

The SIR model is an epidemiological differential model, used to analyze the spread of viral infections, which is based on the collection of three ordinary differential equations using a population N that summarizes susceptible (S), infected (I), and recovered (R) individuals. This model was proposed by Kermack and McKendrick [10], which is described in different functions on a time scale.

This model generates a rate that evolves during an outbreak of a given disease, where the superscript point indicates a temporal derivative. Two of the equations add up to 0 when added together, revealing an underlying assumption that the population remains constant during an outbreak. Mathematically, $S + I + R = N$, regardless of time. This assumption is valid for disease outbreaks of short duration compared to the life expectancy of members of the population [11].

$$(Eq.1) S' = -\beta IS / N, (Eq.2) I' = \beta IS / N - \gamma I, (Eq.3) R' = \gamma I. [11]$$

To understand the model, in the equation (Eq.1) shows S of T (time), which is equivalent to the number of people susceptible to being infected. The S value of 0 is the initial number of susceptible people. In an example of a disease like Covid-19, the S is practically the entire world population. The function I of T (Eq.2) is the number of infected people as a function of time, as well as its initial value I of 0. The value R of T

(Eq.3) is the number of recovered people, where R_0 is the initial number of recovered people. The value N is the sampling value of the population where we have, as already mentioned, the mathematical formula $S + I + R = N$ and will always be a constant [11].

The contact time, during which an infected individual can spread the disease, is represented by the beta parameter. Recovery time is reflected in the gamma parameter. The reproduction number (R_0), which represents the number of persons an infected individual can infect before recovering, is formed by dividing these values by their ratio. As more people develop immunity, the number of susceptible individuals gradually declines, exhibiting an exponential decay. The population that is susceptible decreases as illnesses increase. The number of patients who are infected determines the rate of recovery [12].

The number of individuals who recover after the recovery time (TR) increases together with the number of infected individuals. The susceptible and recovered populations determine how quickly illnesses change. Infections grow exponentially at first, but they diminish as the susceptible population shrinks. The peak happens when the two trends are in balance, and the reproduction number (R_0) determines how steep the curve is [12].

This study uses the SIR model since it makes social media message analysis easier, we can apply that once an individual is exposed to a message, they are susceptible to this pathogen and once infected, in case of reacting the message and typically don't react again, unless opposing it (recovered). The study applies the SIR disease model to message dissemination, focusing on Twitter (X).

3 Methodological Approach

The development approach for the article was exploratory to seek an understanding of how social media users react to certain messages. The necessary bibliographic surveys took place in parallel with the data collection for the pilot for this study. Figure 1 illustrates the steps for the applied study.

Fig. 1. Set of Steps for the development of the work

3.1 Message Topic Selection

Initially, for this work, a survey was carried out on a subject that was popular in the media between January and February 2023, the crisis with the Yanomami indigenous people, and, based on a given message, we analyzed the reactions on the part of the followers from the page. To apply the method, the subject of the Yanomami Indians who live in the Brazilian Amazon was defined in a current context of extreme

vulnerability and a lasting migratory crisis that has plagued the region for years [8]. In addition to being a current issue, it is a matter of humanitarian crisis of great political and economic importance.

3.2 Select Epidemiological Model

To choose the epidemiological method, the SIR model was used in this pilot experiment in an attempt to conceptually adapt individuals who are susceptible to messages on social media and in an attempt to analyze whether they can be infected by the nature of these messages and recover accordingly how they react to posts.

3.3 Select Social Media to Be Monitored

For this pilot, the media selected was Facebook as it has a significant number of followers to facilitate data collection. For the same message, Twitter will also be analyzed in the future, which, like Facebook, in addition to having a large reach due to the large number of users, these media provide means of extracting data for academic studies through tools and libraries.

3.4 Align Model Parameters with Social Media Data

It is possible to observe that the process by which messages are created and spread on social media have many similarities with disease infections. Infection from a particular disease spread through contact; starting when some individuals are infected, so each of these then has contact with others and then, individuals who have had contact with infected people become infected at a certain transmission rate calculated in a certain susceptible population. These infected individuals contact with other individuals, continuing this infection process until there are no more susceptible or infectious individuals [7].

In the context of social media messages, a user who creates a post on any subject becomes an infector and their followers become a population susceptible to this contamination who may read, like, comment or react in some way depending on the resources of the media used. Some followers will share, infecting other people with their posts and so after a certain period, that message stops being shared, losing its power to influence others [7].

The SIR model can be used to understand this dynamic and seek to somehow understand how these social media users become infected and become infectious and count through replicas or counter reactions and analyze whether there is a recovery.

3.5 Identify Message Related to The Topic

This stage sought, within the chosen subject, to find messages that had a significant number of views and comments, coming from a government initiative and thus analyzing the population's reactions.

3.6 Perform Data Collection

Data collection was carried out using the Crowdtangle, a social media analytics tool, which provides certain means of counting reactions and information. We selected a message to monitor sensemaking and a possible degree of contamination (see Table 1). Crowdtangle is a tool that allows to track and monitor post-performance since provided contains data on the performance of posts on a given account. The data includes post text, URL (address), date and time of publication, number of likes, comments and shares, and engagement metrics.

The main information provided by the tools is described in Table 1. The period analyzed was between 01/23/2023 and 02/17/2023.

Table 1. Collected message.

Message	” Governo abre inscrição para ajudar povo Yanomami”
Link	https://www.facebook.com/GloboNews/posts/6367827886583037
Page	https://www.facebook.com/GloboNews/
Followers	2740909
Time Stabilization	7 days
Likes	121
Comments	484
Shares	29
Reaction	24
Views	1680

3.7 Extract rates from the epidemiological model

With the message selected for the experiment with the theme about Yanomami Indians and the collected data, the reactions of the post in a time interval were considered. This interval starts at 15 minutes and increases as reactions increase on social media. To carry out the pilot, 3 different approaches were used. The first one, based on the information collected, python code was used to graphically illustrate the growth of reactions on the timeline. The second one, also through Python code of the SIR model formula, we have the result of a forecast of the follow-up of Susceptible/Infected/Recovered from the information of the first day of follow-up, as described in Table 02. And finally, the third approach, we collected the comment pointed out by the tool as the most relevant, to verify the influence that this message had on users.

In Table 2, the number of followers of the page that posted the message was quantified for those susceptible to the pathogen (message), the infected count those who viewed the message and those who reacted in some way to the message, that is, reacted (Number of reactions = likes+loves+cares+laughs+sadness+rage).

Table 2. Sum of reactions for the sir model.

Category	Total Quantity	Quantity of First day
S (Susceptible)	2740909	2740909
I (Infected)	1680	1319
R (Recovered)	145	109
Asymptomatic Contaminated	1651	1293
Symptomatic Contaminated	29	26

To count asymptomatic infected people, we have to reduce the number of views and the number of shares. And finally, we have that those who shared the message were contaminated by the same showing symptoms.

As a result of the first and second approaches, we were able to visualize the reactions and sums of the categories described in Table 2. Figure 2 and Figure 3 illustrate these results in the mean stabilization time window.

Fig. 2. Number of reactions collected via Crowdtangle.

Fig. 3. Construction of meaning from reactions collected via crowd tangle.

For the analysis of the third approach, we have the comment: “I would like to understand who laughs at a post like that, but he is certainly a disciple of someone who made a gun and said that in his Indian government there would not be another inch of land because his policy was to exterminate them.” This message received 7 likes, 1 sad reaction and 1 negative response.

4 Evaluation Results

Social media allows for quick sharing of content and its users can rate news and information, exchange opinions and provide recommendations. Thus, social networks allow people with similar characteristics or common goals to connect and collaborate on common interests [9].

This initial study showed an analysis of reactions to a message that sought to inform the population about problems of humanitarian origin, showing the construction of meanings from these reactions. It is possible to verify that, despite the large population susceptible to the message, the number of views and reactions is not so large. The growth in quantity on the timeline slows down until it stabilizes, which often occurs in the spread of disease.

From the chosen social media, Facebook, it was possible to extract different types of reactions such as likes, loves, cares, laughs, sadness, and rage. This diversity of emotions is not found on Twitter, for example, where, on the other hand, we can follow the sharing with responses, which would help us understand and better evaluate the amount of contaminated and contaminants used in comparing pandemics with the infodemic study which is the objective of our study.

For this article, when using Facebook, it was possible to raise reactions, because, in addition to the like, there is the "dislike", the heart (more intensity), and the angry face, among the others, mentioned. The comparison between more than one social media further studies are still needed, because the comparison between one result and another also depends on the use of a common method.

5 Final Considerations

This work enables a discussion about the importance of understanding how social media users behave. For example, a message considered to be lying can have negative impacts by influencing users, in this case, it will be desirable to have a low degree of propagation (contamination) and a high rate of quick cures.

On the other hand, in an opposite condition, a message of guidance in the fight against an infectious disease disclosed to the population or messages such as the example used in this article of positive information content in the face of crises, what is desired is a high degree of propagation and influence of that message.

The main limitations found are limited access to messages and their lifetime. We could also observe that the quantified reaction values do not make it clear whether the same user may have chosen more than one different reaction, so we verified that only

quantifying the messages by counting is not enough to have values of the influence of the users' messages.

The study under development intends, in addition to accounting for propagation, to develop a tool to understand the trail of this propagation and its effect on those who had contact with the message or even if there were users who "recovered" after being exposed to the pathogen (message evaluated) and also include different social media.

References

1. Paes, V. J. Araújo, D., K. Brito, and E. Andrade, "Análise de sentimento em tweets relacionados ao desmatamento da floresta Amazonia," in *Anais do XI Brazilian Workshop on Social Network Analysis and Mining*, pp. 61–72, SBC, 2022.
2. K. E. Weick, *Sensemaking in organizations*. Sage Publications, 1995.
3. Y. Yujie, "A survey on information diffusion in online social networks," in *Proceedings of the 2020 European Symposium on Software Engineering, ESSE '20*, (New York, NY, USA), p. 181–186, Association for Computing Machinery, 2020.
4. K. Zhou, T. Wilson, K. Starbird, and E. S. Spiro, "Spotlight tweets: A lens for exploring attention dynamics within online sensemaking during crisis events," *ACM Transactions on Social Computing*, 2023. 9
5. T. França and J. Oliveira, "Análise de sentimento de tweets relacionados aos protestos que ocorreram no brasil entre junho e agosto de 2013," 07 2014.
6. J. C. B. Neves, T. C. de Franca, M. P. Bastos, P. V. R. de Carvalho, and J. O. Gomes, "Analysis of government agencies and stakeholders' twitter communications during the first surge of covid-19 in brazil," *Work*, no. Preprint, pp. 1–13, 2022.
7. J. Woo, J. Son, and H. Chen, "An sir model for violent topic diffusion in social media," in *Proceedings of 2011 IEEE International Conference on Intelligence and Security Informatics*, pp. 15–19, IEEE, 2011.
8. R. C. d. Vasconcelos, "Fronteira em crise: uma avaliação da situação migratória em ro-raima," *Revista de la Secretaria del Tribunal Permanente de Revision*, vol. 11, no. 20, p. 2, 2023.
9. D. H. M. de Araujo, E. A. de Carvalho, A. Jatoba, P. V. R. de Carvalho, and J. O. Gomes, "Social networks applied to dengue, h1n1, and zika epidemics: an integrative literature review," *Work*, vol. 67, no. 3, pp. 721–732, 2020.
10. Kermack William Ogilvy and McKendrick A. G. 1927A contribution to the mathematical theory of epidemics *Proc. R. Soc. Lond.* A115700–721
11. Cannarella, John & Spechler, Joshua. (2014). Epidemiological modeling of online social network dynamics.
12. Meier, Andrea & Peters, Mike. (2023). Limited Engagement of SMEs with Social Media: A Structuration and Sensemaking Perspective. *Information & Management*. 60. 10.1016/j.im.2023.103853.
13. Brill, D., Schnugg, C. & Stary, C. The socio-aesthetic construction of meaning in digitally mediated environments: a digital sensemaking approach. *AI & Soc* (2024).